

Quantification of the cross helicity turbulent cascade in compressible MHD simulations.*VICTOR MONTAGUD-CAMPS ^{2,3}¹*Astronomical Institute, Czech Academy of Sciences, Bocni II/ 1401, CZ-14100 Prague, Czech Republic*²*INAF, Osservatorio Astrofisico di Arcetri, Largo E. Fermi 5, I-50125 Firenze, Italy*³*Università di Firenze, Dipartimento di Fisica e Astronomia, Firenze, Italy*⁴*Istituto di Astrofisica e Planetologia Spaziali, via del Fosso del Cavaliere 100, I-00133 Roma, Italy*⁵*School of Physical and Chemical Sciences, Queen Mary University of London, London E1 4NS, United Kingdom*

(Accepted 2022 September 14)

ABSTRACT

In plasma turbulence, energy and cross helicity are transferred across scales at a constant rate as a consequence of non-linear interactions. In incompressible magnetohydrodynamics (MHD), the energy cascade rate of both quantities can be computed by means of the temporal evolution of second order structure functions, known as Karman–Howarth–Monin (KHM) equations. In the present work, we derive the KHM equation to compute the energy cascade rate of cross helicity in compressible MHD. Using three dimensional direct numerical simulations, we validate the equation and use it to measure the cross helicity turbulence properties. Our results show a slower development of the cross helicity cascade with respect to the energy one and the presence of inverse cascades of energy and cross helicity at large scales when in presence of a strong mean field. We propose the relation of these phenomena with the longer duration of geomagnetic storms after the arrival of solar winds with large cross helicity and the observation of patchy inertial ranges displaying positive and negative cascade rates for certain solar wind intervals.

Keywords: Interplanetary turbulence(830) — Solar wind(1534) — Magnetohydrodynamical simulations(1966) — Heliosphere(711)

1. INTRODUCTION

The solar wind is a turbulent plasma flow where energy is transferred across a vast range of scales. The inertial range is the ensemble of large scales where the cascade of energy is produced by the nonlinear interactions of counter-propagating Alfvén waves (Belcher & Davis 1971). The proportion of Alfvén waves propagating in the anti-sunward (outward) direction can differ from the sunward (inward) propagating ones, with the former being the dominant population. The imbalance between the two populations is known as cross helicity and is equivalent to the correlation between velocity and magnetic field fluctuations.

Such imbalance affects substantially the properties of plasma turbulence in the solar wind (Yokoi & Balarac 2011). Phenomenological models have proposed that high cross helicity inhibit the non-linear transfer of the energy cascade in the solar wind (Dobrowolny et al. 1980; Lithwick et al. 2007; Podesta 2011). This has been supported by estimations of the energy cascade rate computed from solar wind data. For instance, solar wind intervals with large cross helicity presented lower energy cascade rate values than with small cross helicity (Marino et al. 2012). Nevertheless, the transfer of energy from fluctuations in imbalanced solar wind streams provide enough energy to dissipative scales to fulfill the heating required by solar wind proton temperature evolution (Stawarz et al. 2009; Montagud-Camps et al. 2020).

The aforementioned measurements of low cascade rate in solar winds with large cross helicity are not localized in a particular range of scales. Cross helicity, like energy, is an ideal statistical invariant of the incompressible magnetohydrody-

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* Released on XX, Xst, 2022

dynamic (MHD) equations that also cascades to smaller scales at a constant rate over an inertial range. Thus, the study of the cross helicity turbulence by measuring its cascade rate can bring complementary information on the energy cascade in imbalanced solar winds.

The energy cascade rate can be estimated using phenomenological arguments (Vasquez et al. 2007; Zank et al. 2017). However, methods that compute the temporal evolution of second-order structure functions allow to estimate it with the least number of assumptions on the basic equations describing the plasma dynamics. Firstly developed for incompressible hydrodynamics (de Karman & Howarth 1938; Monin & I'Agglom 1971), the Karman–Howarth–Monin (hereafter KHM) equations were then extended to incompressible MHD (Banerjee & Galtier (2017); Politano & Pouquet (1998), hereafter PP98), allowing also for computing separately the cascade rate of cross helicity and energy of the two Alfvén wave populations, known as pseudo-energies. In the following years, the anisotropy of the energy cascade in plasmas with background magnetic field was also taken into account, allowing to quantify it in solar wind observations and numerical simulations (MacBride et al. 2008; Verdini et al. 2015).

The PP98 equations are still widely used to measure the energy cascade rate in the heliosphere. The solar wind, however, is a medium where compressibility can be non-negligible (Hadid et al. (2017)), especially at short heliospheric distances (Shi et al. 2021). This motivated the development of equations to compute the energy cascade rate in plasmas described with the compressible MHD (CMHD) equations (Banerjee & Galtier 2013; Andrés & Sahaoui 2017; Hellinger et al. 2021).

The existence of slow winds in the vicinity of coronal holes with compressible fluctuations and large cross helicity values (D'Amicis & Bruno 2015) led us to extend the KHM equation of cross helicity to compressible MHD.

In this work, the new KHM equation for cross helicity is validated with the data of three-dimensional (3D) CMHD numerical simulations. In addition to cross helicity, the KHM equations for energy and the pseudo-energies are also used to study several properties of the turbulence developed in our simulations, such as spectral anisotropy and directionality of the cascades.

The paper is structured as follows: in section 2 we present the KHM equations of CMHD for energy and cross helicity, as well as the KHM equations of for the pseudo-energies. In section 3 we describe our numerical set-up, in section 4 we present the results of the simulations and the KHM analysis performed on them and section 5 contains the discussion and main conclusions.

2. THEORY

2.1. Karman–Howarth–Monin equations

In this section, the Karman–Howarth–Monin equations for energy and cross helicity are derived from the CMHD equations,

$$\partial_t \rho + (\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla) \rho + \rho \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\partial_t \mathbf{u} + (\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{u} + \frac{1}{\rho} [\nabla P_t - \mathbf{B} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{B}] = \frac{\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau}}{\rho} \quad (2)$$

$$\partial_t \mathbf{B} + (\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{B} - \mathbf{B} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{u} + \mathbf{B} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = \eta \Delta \mathbf{B} \quad (3)$$

$$\partial_t P + (\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla) P + \frac{5}{3} P \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = \rho \kappa \Delta T + \frac{2}{3} \rho Q \quad (4)$$

Quantities in the above equations are normalized with respect to a characteristic length, time, velocity, density and magnetic field $\mathcal{L} = L_0/(2\pi)$, $\mathcal{T} = t_{NL}^0 = L_0/(2\pi u_{rms}^0)$, $\mathbf{U} = u_{rms}^0$, $\rho = \rho_{rms}^0$ and $\mathcal{B} = u_{rms}^0 \sqrt{4\pi \rho_{rms}^0}$, where the superscript 0 denotes the value of the quantity at the initial time and the subscript *rms* denotes the root-mean-square of the quantity.

In equation 2, the viscous stress-tensor is $\tau_{ij} = \mu(\partial_j u_i + \partial_i u_j - (2/3)\delta_{ij}\partial_k u_k)$, the total pressure is $P_t = P + B^2/2$ and $P = \rho T$ is the plasma thermal pressure. In equation 4, the turbulent heating per unit volume is $Q \equiv \left(\mathbf{w} \cdot \frac{\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau}}{\sqrt{\rho}} + \eta |\mathbf{J}|^2 \right)$, where $\mathbf{w} = \sqrt{\rho} \mathbf{u}$ is the density-weighted velocity (Kida & Orszag 1990), $\mathbf{J} = \nabla \times \mathbf{B}$ is the current density and μ , η , κ are respectively the dynamic viscosity, resistivity and thermal conductivity.

One of the aims of this work is to assess the influence of thermal compressibility in the cross-helicity cascade. Cross-helicity is not an ideal statistical invariant in CMHD, that is, it is no longer conserved when dissipation processes are negligible. Nonetheless, a conservation law can be obtained from equations 1-4,

$$\frac{\partial \langle \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{B} \rangle}{\partial t} = \left\langle P \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{\mathbf{B}}{\rho} \right) \right\rangle - Q_H \quad (5)$$

where $\langle \dots \rangle$ denotes the volume averaging and the dissipative rate for cross-helicity is $Q_H \equiv \left\langle \left(\mathbf{B} \cdot \frac{\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau}}{\rho} + \eta (\boldsymbol{\omega} \cdot \mathbf{J}) \right) \right\rangle$. The first term on the right-hand side of equation 5 is the average pressure-dilatation term and allows to measure the departure of cross helicity from an ideal conservation law. The same apply to the conservation of free energy in CMHD, that takes the form

$$\frac{\partial \langle \mathbf{w}^2 + \mathbf{B}^2 \rangle}{\partial t} = \langle P \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} \rangle - Q_E \quad (6)$$

where $Q_E = \langle Q \rangle$.

Even when the pressure-dilatation terms are non negligible, the KHM equations can still be derived from the evolution of second order structure functions. These are computed as $S_2 \equiv \langle \delta \mathbf{a} \cdot \delta \mathbf{b} \rangle$, where $\delta \mathbf{a}$ is defined as $\delta \mathbf{a}(\boldsymbol{\ell}) \equiv \mathbf{a}(\mathbf{x}') - \mathbf{a}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{a}' - \mathbf{a}$ denotes the spatial increment of the vector field \mathbf{a} between pairs of points \mathbf{x} and $\mathbf{x}' = \boldsymbol{\ell} + \mathbf{x}$.

It is common to express the KHM equations in such a way that the non-linear transfer takes the form of a flux of third order structure functions. Following the same procedure used in Hellinger et al. (2021) to obtain the KHM equation of energy for compressible Hall MHD, we derived the expression for the non-linear transfer of cross-helicity for CMHD

$$K_H = -\frac{1}{4} \nabla_{\boldsymbol{\ell}} \cdot \left\langle \left[\delta \mathbf{u} (\delta \mathbf{u} \cdot \delta \mathbf{B}) - \delta \mathbf{B} \frac{1}{2} |\delta \mathbf{u}|^2 \right] \right. \\ \left. - \left[\delta \mathbf{B} \cdot \delta \left(\frac{\mathbf{J}}{\rho} \times \mathbf{B} \right) + (\nabla' \cdot \mathbf{u}') (\delta \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{B}) - (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}) (\delta \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{B}') \right] \right\rangle \quad (7)$$

where $\nabla' = \nabla_{\mathbf{x}'}$ and $\nabla = \nabla_{\mathbf{x}}$.

The first term on the right-hand side of equation 7 allows to measure part of the contribution of incompressible fluctuations to the cross helicity cascade rate from solar wind observations, provided some assumption on turbulence anisotropy is made. However, measuring the flux of third order structure functions in numerical simulations is highly computationally demanding. The calculation of spatial increments between every pair $(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}')$ in three-dimensional simulations requires N^6 operations, being N the number of grid-points in one direction.

A way to substantially reduce the computational cost of this process consists on using the cross-correlation property of the Fourier transform on the right-hand side of the following identity

$$\langle \delta \mathbf{a} \cdot \delta \mathbf{b} \rangle = 2 \langle \mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{b} \rangle - \langle \mathbf{a}' \cdot \mathbf{b} + \mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{b}' \rangle \quad (8)$$

leading to

$$\langle \delta \mathbf{a} \cdot \delta \mathbf{b} \rangle = 2 \langle \mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{b} \rangle - \mathcal{F}^{-1} \left(\hat{\mathbf{a}}^* \cdot \hat{\mathbf{b}} + \hat{\mathbf{a}} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{b}}^* \right) \quad (9)$$

where $\mathcal{F}^{-1}(\dots)$ denotes the inverse Fourier transform, $\hat{\mathbf{a}} = \int_{\mathbf{x}} \mathbf{a} \cdot e^{i\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{x}}$ is the direct Fourier Transform and $\hat{\mathbf{a}}^*$ denotes the complex conjugate of $\hat{\mathbf{a}}$.

In this way, the number of operations is reduced to that of a Fast Fourier Transform, $(N \cdot \log(N))^3$. In order to take advantage of this improvement in computational efficiency, we used equation 9 to derived alternative versions of the KHM equations of energy and cross helicity for CMHD and for the pseudo-energies in incompressible MHD.

2.1.1. Energy and Cross-helicity

From equations 1-3, the KHM equations for energy and cross helicity can be obtained using identity 9 and read

$$-\frac{1}{4} \frac{\partial S_i}{\partial t} + K_i + \Phi_i - D_i = 0 \quad (10)$$

where the subscript $i = E$ corresponds to energy and $i = H$ to cross helicity. The temporal decay KHM terms are defined as,

$$S_E(\boldsymbol{\ell}) = \frac{1}{2} \langle |\delta \mathbf{w}|^2 + |\delta \mathbf{B}|^2 \rangle \quad (11)$$

$$S_H(\boldsymbol{\ell}) = \langle \delta \mathbf{u} \cdot \delta \mathbf{B} \rangle \quad (12)$$

The temporal variation of these terms in equation 10 is computed using a forward finite difference method with a time-shift of $\Delta t = 10^{-2} t_{NL}^0$. For the other terms, we take the average value between the two times.

The non-linear transfer terms of equation 10 read

$$K_E(\boldsymbol{\ell}) = -\frac{1}{4} \langle \delta \mathbf{w} \cdot \delta [(\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{w} + \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{w} \cdot \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}] \\ - \delta \mathbf{w} \cdot \delta (\rho^{-1/2} (\nabla \times \mathbf{B}) \times \mathbf{B}) - \delta \mathbf{B} \cdot \delta (\nabla \times (\mathbf{u} \times \mathbf{B})) \rangle > \quad (13)$$

$$K_H(\boldsymbol{\ell}) = -\frac{1}{4} \langle \delta \mathbf{B} \cdot \delta ((\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{u}) - \delta \mathbf{B} \cdot \delta (\rho^{-1} (\nabla \times \mathbf{B}) \times \mathbf{B}) \\ - \delta \mathbf{u} \cdot \delta (\nabla \times (\mathbf{u} \times \mathbf{B})) \rangle > \quad (14)$$

The compressible terms associated to pressure-dilatation effects are

$$\Phi_E(\boldsymbol{\ell}) = -\frac{1}{4} \langle \delta \mathbf{w} \cdot \delta (\rho^{-1/2} \nabla P) \rangle \quad (15)$$

$$\Phi_H(\boldsymbol{\ell}) = -\frac{1}{4} \langle \delta \mathbf{B} \cdot \delta (\rho^{-1} \nabla P) \rangle \quad (16)$$

and the terms containing dissipative effects

$$D_E(\boldsymbol{\ell}) = -\frac{1}{4} \langle \delta \mathbf{w} \cdot \delta (\rho^{-1/2} \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau}) + \eta \delta \mathbf{B} \cdot \delta (\Delta \mathbf{B}) \rangle \quad (17)$$

$$D_H(\boldsymbol{\ell}) = -\frac{1}{4} \langle \delta \mathbf{B} \cdot \delta (\rho^{-1} \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau}) + \eta \delta \mathbf{u} \cdot \delta (\Delta \mathbf{B}) \rangle \quad (18)$$

We remark that D_i terms tend to the turbulent heatings Q_i at the largest separation scale. That is, $D_i - Q_i$ represent the effect of the dissipative mechanisms in the system. However, in order to see more clearly the contributions of each term in equations 10 we do not subtract the total heatings to D_i . In addition, we simply name D_i as *dissipative terms*, despite being an abuse of language.

2.1.2. Pseudo-energies

Using again equations 2 and 3, and assuming incompressibility one can write the equations for the Elsässer fields

$\mathbf{z}^\pm = \mathbf{u} \pm \mathbf{B} / \sqrt{\rho_{rms}^0}$ as follows

$$\partial_t \mathbf{z}^\pm + (\mathbf{z}^\mp \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{z}^\pm + \nabla \left(P + \frac{B^2}{2} \right) = \frac{(\mu \pm \eta)}{2} \Delta \mathbf{z}^+ + \frac{(\mu \mp \eta)}{2} \Delta \mathbf{z}^- \quad (19)$$

The third term on the left-hand side does not contribute to the KHM equations if local homogeneity is also assumed (Carbone et al. 2009). Under these conditions the pressure-dilatation terms can be omitted from the KHM equations of the pseudo-energies.

$$-\frac{1}{4} \frac{\partial \mathcal{S}_\pm}{\partial t} + K_\pm - D_\pm \quad (20)$$

where the temporal decay terms are

$$\mathcal{S}_\pm(\ell) = \left\langle \frac{(\delta \mathbf{z}^\pm)^2}{2} \right\rangle \quad (21)$$

the non-linear transfer terms read

$$K_\pm(\ell) = -\frac{1}{4} \langle \delta \mathbf{z}^\pm \cdot \delta [(\mathbf{z}^\mp \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{z}^\pm] \rangle \quad (22)$$

and the dissipative terms are

$$D_\pm(\ell) = -\frac{1}{4} \left\langle \frac{(\mu \pm \eta)}{2} \delta \mathbf{z}^+ \cdot \delta [\Delta \mathbf{z}^+] + \frac{(\mu \mp \eta)}{2} \delta \mathbf{z}^- \cdot \delta [\Delta \mathbf{z}^-] \right\rangle \quad (23)$$

From equations 21 to 23, it is possible to compute the KHM terms for energy in incompressible MHD as

$$\mathcal{S}_{zE} = \frac{\mathcal{S}_+ + \mathcal{S}_-}{2}, K_{zE} = \frac{K_+ + K_-}{2}, D_{zE} = \frac{D_+ + D_-}{2} \quad (24)$$

and for cross-helicity

$$\mathcal{S}_{zH} = \frac{\mathcal{S}_+ - \mathcal{S}_-}{2}, K_{zH} = \frac{K_+ - K_-}{2}, D_{zH} = \frac{D_+ - D_-}{2} \quad (25)$$

where we have denoted incompressible energy and cross helicity as $zE = E^+ + E^-$ and $zH = E^+ - E^-$ respectively.

3. NUMERICAL SET-UP

The 3D CMHD equations have been solved using a pseudo-spectral method to compute spatial gradients and a Runge-Kutta order three scheme for the evolution in time (Wray 1990). The numerical domain is a box with edge length $2\pi\mathcal{L}$, periodic boundary conditions and a uniform mesh of 512 grid-points in each direction.

Two numerical simulations are analyzed in this work: one without a mean magnetic field, run A, and one with an ambient magnetic field $\mathbf{B}_0 = (4, 0, 0)b_{rms}^0$, run B. Velocity and magnetic fluctuations have been excited with random phases in all directions for run A, and in the planes perpendicular

to the ambient magnetic field for run B. For both runs, magnetic and velocity fluctuation amplitudes are initially equal, $u_{rms}^0 \sim b_{rms}^0 \sim 1$, the initial normalized cross-helicity is $\sigma_c = \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{B} / (u^2 + B^2) = 0.8$, and the initial turbulent Mach number is $M = u_{rms} / c_s = 0.85$ with $c_s = \sqrt{(5/3)T}$. The isotropic magnetic and kinetic energy spectra have a flat initial slope, excited up to a cut-off wave number $k_{max} = 4$ for both runs. All other fluctuations have zero amplitude at the beginning of the simulation. No forcing is applied to any fluctuations.

Dynamic viscosity, resistivity and thermal conductivity have been chosen in order to avoid the accumulation of energy at mesh-size scales and, at the same time, maximize the kinetic and magnetic Reynolds numbers. In order to simplify the selection of the optimal values, we have imposed $\mu = \eta = \kappa$. For run A, $\mu, \eta, \kappa = 1.5 \cdot 10^{-3}$ and for run B, $\mu, \eta, \kappa = 8 \cdot 10^{-4}$.

4. RESULTS

4.1. Turbulence properties

In this section we present the temporal evolution of several relevant plasma parameters, as well as the isotropic spectra after the onset of turbulence.

The peak of turbulent activity for the energy cascade in numerical simulations is taken at the moment the dissipation of turbulent fluctuations has reached a maximum that is followed-up by a period of constant dissipation, an indication that turbulence is fully developed. The impossibility to write an explicit expression for turbulent heating in certain numerical simulations leads to use other ways to estimate the peak of turbulent activity, such as the measure of the volume average of squared current density, $\langle J^2 \rangle$, or the vorticity, $\langle \omega^2 \rangle$, both included in our expression of the energy heating rate Q_E .

The maximum of $\langle J^2 \rangle$ is, approximately at $2.5 t_{NL}^0$ for run A and at $6 t_{NL}^0$ for run B, as shown in the figures 1(a) and figure 1(b), respectively. The same figures shows also that the peaks of vorticity, $\langle \omega^2 \rangle$, happen at $2 t_{NL}^0$ and $6 t_{NL}^0$ for runs A and B respectively.

The peak of turbulent activity for the cross-helicity cascade can be considered as the maximum of $\langle \mathbf{J} \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega} \rangle$, that plays a role in cross helicity turbulent heating, Q_H , equivalent to the one played by $\langle J^2 \rangle$ for Q_E . The peaks of $\langle \mathbf{J} \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega} \rangle$ occur at later times than for $\langle J^2 \rangle$ and $\langle \omega^2 \rangle$: $3 t_{NL}^0$ for run A and $7 t_{NL}^0$ for run B.

Figures 1(c) and 1(d) show that the temporal evolution of the average pressure-dilatation $\langle P \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} \rangle$ and $\langle P \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{B} / \rho) \rangle$ and the heating rates for energy and cross-helicity Q_E and Q_H , for runs A and B respectively.

The maximum of cross-helicity heating takes place in both runs at the same time that $\langle \mathbf{J} \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega} \rangle$ peaks in fig. 1(a) and (b), therefore indicating the importance of $\langle \mathbf{J} \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega} \rangle$ structures in the dissipation of cross helicity. The maxima of Q_E are reached at the same time as $\langle \omega^2 \rangle$.

The average pressure-dilatation decrease substantially after the peaks of Q_E . From that moment onwards, the average pressure-dilatation terms remain at least one order of magnitude smaller than the heating rates for run A. For run B, the ratio between average pressure-dilatation terms and Q_E and Q_H are even smaller. In other words, the development of turbulence and the presence of a background mean magnetic field substantially reduces the pressure dilatation term in the conservation equations 6 and 5 and therefore $\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{B}$ and $\mathbf{w}^2 + \mathbf{B}^2$ become closer to ideal statistical invariants of CMHD.

Figure 1. Panels (a), (c) and (e) corresponds to run A and panels (b), (d) and (f) to run B. (a) and (b): temporal evolution of the volume average current density squared $\langle J^2 \rangle$ (solid lines), vorticity $\langle \omega^2 \rangle$ (dotted lines) and cross-current $\langle \mathbf{J} \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega} \rangle$ (dashed lines). (c) and (d): temporal evolution of the averaged pressure-dilatation term for energy $\langle P\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} \rangle$ (magenta lines) and cross-helicity $\langle P\nabla \cdot (\frac{\mathbf{B}}{\rho}) \rangle$ (purple lines) and for the turbulent heating of energy Q_E (red lines) and cross helicity (brown lines). (e) and (f): temporal evolution of normalized cross-helicity σ_c (black line), turbulent Mach number (yellow line) and root mean square of density fluctuations (green line).

The small amplitudes for the pressure-dilatations are obtained under relatively high turbulent Mach number, $M = u_{rms}/c_s$ with $c_s = \sqrt{(5/3)T}$, that descends from 0.8 to 0.6 in both runs (figure 1(e) for run A and 1(f) for run B). The same panels show how, during a short period of relaxation for the initial conditions, there is a short increase of density fluctuations $\Delta\rho = \langle \langle \rho \rangle - \rho \rangle$. After reaching its maximum around $0.2\rho_{rms}^0$, it decrease monotonically. Conversely, the normalized cross-helicity, $\sigma_c = \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{B}/(\mathbf{u}^2 + \mathbf{B}^2)$, increases with time after the relaxation period of the initial conditions, as is characteristic of numerical simulations without expansion of the plasma (Grappin et al. (1982), Grappin et al. (2016)). The presence of the mean magnetic field in run B slows down the temporal evolution of these plasma parameters, but maintains their overall behaviour.

Figures 2 (a) and (b) show respectively the spectra of magnetic and kinetic fluctuations computed at the peaks of cross-helicity turbulence: at $3t_{NL}^0$ for run A and at $7t_{NL}^0$ for run B. In fig. 2(a), magnetic and kinetic fluctuations have an isotropic spectra with a slope of -2 . In fig. 2(b), the slopes are slightly steeper, proportional to $k^{-2.2}$. These spectral indices are steeper than the $-5/3$ of the Kolmogorov's prediction (Kolmogorov 1941) or the $-3/2$ of the Irishnikov-Kraichnan phenomenology (Irshnikov 1963; Kraichnan 1965), being closer to the -2 predicted for weak MHD turbulence (Galtier et al. 2000) or the -2 predicted by Burger's for shock-based turbulence phenomenology (Frisch 1995). The former two phenomenologies are unlikely to explain the observed spectra in our simulations. Weak turbulence takes place when magnetic fluctuations are at least an order of magnitude smaller than the mean field (Meyrand et al. 2015) and this phenomenology would not be able to explain the -2 index in the run with no background magnetic field. On the other hand, Burger's phenomenology can also be discarded attending to the fact that both runs were initialized with subsonic fluctuations and no substantial amount of shocks can be developed in a pseudo-spectral code, such as the one we are using.

The spectral indices in our simulations respond instead to the inefficiency of non-linear interactions to produce an effective energy transfer, caused by the initial imbalance of the alfvénic populations and the difficulty to achieve higher Reynolds numbers. The inefficiency of the cascade is further commented in section 4.2.

The kinetic and magnetic spectra are almost superposed in both cases, except for $k < 2$, where there is a small magnetic excess for both runs. The spectra of the pseudo-energies $E^+ = |\mathbf{z}^+|^2/2$ and $E^- = |\mathbf{z}^-|^2/2$ are computed at the same time as the velocity and the magnetic spectra and are shown in figure 2(c) for run A and figure 2(d) for run B. Both runs show dominance of the \mathbf{z}^+ Alfvén wave energy over that of

Figure 2. Top row: isotropized spectra of magnetic (orange lines) and velocity fluctuations (green lines) for run A at $t = 3t_{NL}^0$ (figure (a)) and run B at $t = 7t_{NL}^0$ (figure (b)). Bottom row: spectra of the pseudo-energies E^+ (red lines) and E^- (blue lines) for run A at $t = 3t_{NL}^0$ (figure (c)) and run B at $t = 7t_{NL}^0$ (figure (d)).

z^- , with the spectra of the former steeper than the latter. In the solar wind, these spectra remain almost parallel at inertial range scales (Chen et al. 2020). Conversely, the pinning of the Elsässer spectra is characteristic of simulations that do not account for expansion of the solar wind in the directions transverse to the heliospheric radial (Verdini et al. 2019).

4.2. Energy and Cross-helicity cascades in compressible MHD

Figure 3 shows the KHM terms of energy and cross helicity isotropized in separation-space, so they only depend on the modulus of ℓ .

We have selected three times to show the temporal evolution of the KHM terms for energy and cross-helicity close to their respective peaks of turbulent activity. For run A, $t_1 = 1t_{NL}^0$ corresponds to one turnover time prior to the peak of the energy heating rate, which occurs at $t_2 = 2t_{NL}^0$. Finally, $t_3 = 3t_{NL}^0$ is taken at the peak of the cross-helicity heating rate.

Conversely, for run B, the first time is the maximum energy heating rate, $t_1 = 6t_{NL}^0$, and $t_2 = 7t_{NL}^0$ is the peak of Q_H . As it will be further explained later in this section, the temporal decay term of energy grows in the inertial range at $7t_{NL}^0$ and becomes non-negligible. In order to discard that our conclusions on the energy and cross helicity cascades of run B could be attributed to a short-lived phenomenon, we chose $t_3 = 8t_{NL}^0$, when the temporal decay term is again negligible within the inertial range.

The KHM terms at time t_1 in fig. 3(a)-(d) are represented with dashed lines, t_2 with dotted lines and t_3 with solid lines. All KHM terms are normalized to energy heating rate, Q_E , of their respective run and time. This normalization allows for an easy comparison of the efficiency of the non-linear transfer of the energy and the cross helicity cascades.

The KHM terms of energy and cross helicity fulfill equation 10 for all three times in run A, with errors (black lines) smaller than $1\%Q_E$. The presence of a mean magnetic field in run B is not reflected on the error O_ℓ , that also remains below $1\%Q_E$ at all times.

The time delay between the peaks of Q_E and Q_H for run A observed in fig. 1(c) can be seen in terms of the evolution of the temporal decay terms (blue lines) in figures 3(a) and 3(c). During the onset of the cascades, the decay terms of energy and cross helicity present negative values at intermediate scales. At the peak of Q_E , the energy decay terms are already close to zero for $\ell < 0.5$ while this does not happen to cross helicity until the peak of Q_H .

In figure 3(b), the temporal decay terms of the energy cascade for run B is close to zero for scales $\ell < 0.5$ at $t_1 = 6t_{NL}^0$. Like for run A, cross helicity decay terms will not reach this situation until the peak of Q_H at $t_2 = 7t_{NL}^0$ (fig. 3(d)). Thus, the KHM analysis also confirms that the slower development of the cross-helicity cascade is not affected by the presence of a background magnetic field.

We remark that for run B, there is a non-negligible increase of the temporal decay term of energy at $t_2 = 7t_{NL}^0$ for all scales (see fig. 3 (b)). This increase is only temporary and the decay term decreases back to its previous state after a turnover time, at $t_3 = 8t_{NL}^0$. This fluctuation of the decay term also alters the non-linear transfer of energy (green lines).

In the absence of the KHM analysis, one could assume that at $t_2 = 7t_{NL}^0$ the turbulence is already well developed based on the temporal evolution of Q_E or $\langle J^2 \rangle$, leading to conclusions on the energy cascade rate that could not be valid after a non-linear time. Thus, even though the dissipation rates Q_E and Q_H (or $\langle J^2 \rangle$ and $\langle \mathbf{J} \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega} \rangle$ in the absence of an explicit expression for the heating) can be considered as good proxies to establish the maximum of turbulence activity, the KHM analysis provides a more accurate description of the turbulence properties at all scales, allowing to detect transitory changes of the cascades that would be unnoticed otherwise.

The KHM dissipative terms, $-D_E$ and $-D_H$, also display the slower development of the cross helicity cascade, although less clearly than the temporal decay terms. Figure 3(a) shows that the energy dissipation terms already converge after t_2 while the cross-helicity dissipative terms in fig. 3(c) still show some differences between times t_2 and t_3 . Con-

versely, for run B the dissipation terms of energy and cross helicity in fig. 3(b) fig. 3(d) are almost completely superposed for all three times. Thus, the dissipative process seems to be more stable in presence of the mean magnetic field. This is compatible with the small temporal variations of the heating rates Q_E and Q_H in fig. 1(d) once their respective maxima have been reached. Taking into consideration that the magnetic reconnection rate in Hall MHD simulations is reduced by strong guide fields (Pritchett & Coroniti 2004; Huba 2005; Tharp et al. 2013; Widmer et al. 2016), the stability of the dissipative process in run B might also be related to the influence of the mean field on the current sheets and the effect of these structures on the heating process.

The evolution of the flows towards the maxima of turbulence activity does not have any remarkable effect on the KHM pressure-dilatation terms Φ_E and Φ_H , besides a decrease of their amplitude in time. These KHM terms reach their maxima at large scales, generally around $\ell > 1$. The amplitude of Φ_E is larger than Φ_H at all times and for both runs. In figures 3(a) and 3(c), Φ_H for run A have opposite sign to Φ_E , but this does not happen in figures 3(b) and 3(d) for run B.

In the latter, the pressure-dilatation KHM terms oscillate around zero and their amplitudes are between two and five times smaller than for run A. Thus, the presence of a background magnetic field reduces the pressure-dilatation effects in turbulence and favors the changes of sign of Φ_E and Φ_H . However, the oscillations of the pressure-dilatation term can still be developed even in absence of the mean field, provided that the simulation is allowed to evolve for a long enough time. The application of the KHM equation of energy for three-dimensional compressible hydrodynamic simulations proved that the oscillations can also appear in isotropic turbulent flows (Hellinger et al. 2021).

The non-linear transfer terms K_E and K_H of runs A and B at the peaks of turbulent activity show that the energy and cross helicity cascade are not efficient enough in our simulations. All non-linear transfer terms peak at intermediate scales, approximately at $\ell \approx 3$, and do not reach critical heating levels. For the cross helicity cascade, that level should be reached at $Q_H \approx 0.7Q_E$ for run A and $Q_H \approx 0.5Q_E$ for run B. The range of scales where K_E and K_H values are close to their maxima is also narrow, not much more than half a decade.

The relatively large turbulent Mach number with which we set-up the simulations limited our capacity to achieve higher Reynolds numbers and therefore, contributed to limit the extension of the inertial ranges and the efficiency of the non-linear transfers. However, for run B, the isotropization of the KHM terms in figures 3(b) and 3(d) hides the improvement of the efficiency of the cascades in the directions transverse to

the mean magnetic field. This point will be further discussed in section 4.5.

In spite of the limited efficiency of the cascades, the K_E and K_H show one remarkable trait. For run B, the non-linear transfers of energy and cross helicity split in two: scales below $\ell \approx 1$ present positive K_E and K_H values and negative ones for scales above $\ell \approx 1$. After the onset of turbulence, the splitting of the cascades does not take place for run A, signaling the importance of the background magnetic field for this process.

In run A, once the peak of Q_E is reached, K_E and K_H are positive and $K_E \geq K_H$ at all scales. The latter means that the non-linear transfer of energy is more efficient than that of cross helicity. In the range of scales where the non-linear transfers are positive for run B, $K_E \geq K_H$ too. Conversely, the opposite happens in the range of negative values, where the non-linear transfer of the cross helicity cascade is the more efficient of the two. This feature of the non-linear transfer for run B is not short-lived and remains for several turn-over times, until the end of the simulation (not shown).

We will discuss the splitting of the energy and cross helicity cascades in detail in section 5.

4.3. Estimation of the cascade rate for the pseudo-energies.

The pseudo-energies E^+ and E^- are ideal statistical invariants of the incompressible MHD equations that, like energy and cross-helicity, cascade through a range of scales as a result of non-linear interactions. Assuming that compressible effects are negligible, the incompressible energy and cross helicity can be written in terms of the Elsässer energies as $zE \equiv E^+ + E^-$ and $zH \equiv E^+ - E^-$ respectively. Consequently, the KHM terms of E^+ and E^- allow to interpret the non-linear transfers in terms of the outward and inward Alfvén wave populations.

In this section, we compute the KHM terms of the pseudo-energies as defined in equations 21-23 and use them to study the splitting of the energy and cross helicity cascades in run B. Figure 4 presents the KHM terms of E^+ and E^- computed at $t = 8$ and normalized to the energy heating rate Q_E .

Since E_+ is the dominant Alfvén wave population, its KHM terms resemble those of the energy cascade in fig. 3(b). However, for scales $\ell > 1$, the negative values of the non-linear transfer K_+ are closer to the the cross helicity ones in fig. 3(d). But unlike cross helicity, the pseudo-energies are positive definite and therefore the negative values of K_+ imply that an inverse cascade of E^+ is taking place at large scales.

This inverse cascade of E^+ exists even if the error introduced by the assumption of incompressibility is taken into account. Such error is represented as the solid black line in

Figure 3. Temporal evolution of the Karman-Howarth-Monin terms of energy and cross-helicity for runs A and B. The KHM terms have been computed at $t_1 = 1t_{NL}^0$, $t_2 = 2t_{NL}^0$ and $t_3 = 3t_{NL}^0$ for run A and at $t_1 = 6t_{NL}^0$, $t_2 = 7t_{NL}^0$ and $t_3 = 8t_{NL}^0$ for run B. The validity test O_t are represented by black lines. The other lines correspond to the dissipative terms D_i (red lines); the temporal decay $\partial S_i/\partial t/4$ (blue lines); the non-linear transfer rate term K_i (green lines) and the pressure dilatation term Φ_i (magenta lines), where the subscript $i = E$ denotes the energy KHM terms and $i = H$ the cross helicity ones.

fig. 4. It is concentrated at large scales $\ell > 0.8$, where it reaches about $30\%Q_E$. The positive sign in the error implies that, due to compressibility, the energy transfer rate at large scales could be between the maximum of K_+ , $-40\%Q_E$ and, at most, $-70\%Q_E$. The last value is obtained assuming that K_+ is the only KHM term of E^+ affected by compressible effects.

For the subdominant pseudo-energy E^- , the non-linear transfer term K_- is always positive and therefore corresponds to a direct cascade of E^- . Like before, even if the error associated to the incompressible assumption (dashed black line in fig. 4) is completely assigned to K_- , that would not change the direction of the cascade of E^- towards small scales.

4.4. Effect of compressibility in the energy and cross helicity cascade estimations.

In the classic formulation of the KHM equations of energy and cross helicity, the incompressible and compressible contributions to the non-linear transfers are separated into different terms (see eq.7). With the alternative KHM equations we presented in section 2.1.1, it is not possible to directly isolate the compressible contributions. However, it can be done by comparing the KHM terms for CMHD with the incompressible ones for energy, zE and cross helicity zH .

Figures 5(a) and 5(b) show with dashed lines the KHM terms for energy and cross helicity for CMHD, computed for run B at $t = 8t_{NL}^0$ according to equations 11 - 18. Conversely, solid lines correspond to the KHM terms for energy and cross-helicity computed from the Elsässer fields following equations 24 and 25.

The comparison in fig. 5(a) between the non-linear transfer of energy computed from the Elsässer fields, K_{zE} and

the transfer computed from CMHD, K_E , proves that compressibility favors the direct cascade of energy towards small scales. On the one hand, both quantities are positive and peak at $\ell \approx 0.3$, where K_E is approximately 10% Q_E larger than K_{zE} . On the other hand, their minima is reached at $\ell \approx 3$, where both quantities are negative and K_{zE} is almost 20% Q_E smaller than K_E . Therefore, compressibility not only enhances the direct cascade of energy, but also contributes to inhibit its large scale inverse cascade.

Compressibility plays a more complex role on the cross-helicity turbulent cascade. In fig. 5(b), At scales larger than $\ell \approx 0.3$, K_H is always below K_{zH} . Both transfers are positive for $\ell \lesssim 1$ and change the sign at larger scales. Consequently, above $\ell \approx 0.3$ compressible fluctuations inhibit the positive transfer of cross helicity and enhance the negative one. At scales smaller than $\ell \approx 0.3$ however, K_H is larger than K_{zH} , indicating that compressibility benefits the positive transfer of cross helicity at these scales.

The incompressible version of the KHM terms for energy and cross helicity provide a good approximation, not only of the positive non-linear transfer, but of the other KHM terms too. For scales below $\ell \approx 0.3$ the non-linear transfers of energy and cross helicity are positive and are the main contributors to the total error (solid black lines in figures 5(a) and 5(b)), that does not surpass 10% of the energy and cross helicity heating rates.

On the contrary, at large scales, where the negative non-linear transfer takes place for both cascades, the total error of the incompressible KHM equations becomes considerably larger, specially for cross helicity. While for incompressible energy, zE , the total error amounts to 20% Q_E , for zH it rises up to 70% Q_H . Hence, compressible fluctuations have greater presence at large scales.

4.5. Anisotropy of the energy and cross helicity cascades

In this section, the anisotropy of the energy and the cross helicity cascades of run B are analyzed by taking three one-dimensional (1D) cuts of the KHM terms of CMHD before its isotropization. The cuts are taken at $t = 8t_{NL}^0$ in the direction of the mean field, the x axis ($\theta_B = 0^\circ$), along the y axis ($\theta_B = 90^\circ$) and along the bisector of both axis ($\theta_B = 45^\circ$).

Panels (a), (b) and (c) of figure (6) show the anisotropy of the KHM terms for the energy cascade. All KHM terms for energy are normalized to the energy heating rate of the whole numerical domain, Q_E .

In panel (a), the non-linear transfer is positive along the mean magnetic field direction, although it reaches only moderate values, 20% Q_E for scales $\ell < 0.8$. The dissipative effects are already non-negligible at those scales. For larger scales, K_E takes large negative values, even below $-1Q_E$.

Figure 4. Isotropized KHM terms for the pseudo-energies E^+ (solid lines) and E^- (dashed lines) as a function of separation scale ℓ , computed for run B at time $t = 8t_{NL}^0$, after the peaks of maximum turbulent activity for energy and cross helicity. All terms are normalized to the energy heating rate Q_E . The color code is the same as in figure 3.

The temporal decay term rises above the Q_E line in order to balance the back transfer of energy.

The pressure dilatation terms for energy, Φ_E , in figures 6(a)-6(c) are only non negligible at scales larger than $\ell > 0.8$, but even there their absolute value remains below 10% Q_E . The sign of Φ_E changes with the inclination θ_B but, unlike the other terms, it does not display any clear anisotropy.

Figures 6(b) and 6(c) show that the non-linear transfer term for energy increases at all scales when approaching the directions transverse to the mean field. In fig. 6(c), there is a well developed inertial range within $\ell \in [0.1, 1]$, where the non-linear term reaches $K_E \approx 80\%Q_E$. In 6(b) we already see large positive values of K_E , but with some fluctuations for $\ell > 0.3$.

In panel 6(c), for scales $\ell > 2$ perpendicular to \mathbf{B}_0 there is an inverse non-linear transfer, but it only reaches $-40\%Q_E$. This back transfer seems restricted to almost perpendicular scales. Large scales in 6(b) do not show negative values of K_E along $\theta_B = 45^\circ$.

The dissipative terms along 45° and 90° increase for separation scales smaller than 0.2, which is compatible with an energy cascade developed predominantly in the directions perpendicular to the ambient magnetic field.

The temporal decay terms anisotropy seems to be adapted to that of the non linear transfer terms, so it can maintain equation 10 valid in all directions.

The cross-helicity turbulence anisotropy is analyzed in panels (d), (e) and (f) of fig (6). The KHM terms of cross

Figure 5. (a) Isotropized KHM terms of energy E (dashed lines) and $zE = E^+ + E^-$ (solid lines) for run B at $t = 8t_{NL}^0$. (b) Isotropized KHM terms of cross helicity H (dashed lines) and $zH = E^+ - E^-$ (solid lines) for run B at $t = 8t_{NL}^0$. The color code is the same as in figure 3.

helicity are normalized to Q_H computed on the whole numerical domain.

The anisotropy of the cross helicity cascade is qualitatively similar to the energy cascade one in what regards the dissipative and the pressure dilatation terms. The non-linear transfer term K_H in 6(f) also presents an extended inertial range in the direction perpendicular to B_0 , within the scales $\ell \in [0.3, 1]$, where $K_H \approx 70\%Q_H$.

As it was already seen when comparing the isotropic KHM terms in figures 3(b) and 3(d), the negative values of K_H in 6(f) are more than four times greater than for K_E in 6(c) and over a longer range of scales, $\ell > 1$.

However, for the cross helicity cascade, it is not clear whether this large scales behaviour of K_H is only restricted to highly oblique inclinations. In 6(e) one can observe the variations of the non-linear transfer term, similar to K_E in 6(b), but with larger amplitude.

In order to have a more complete view of the variations of the non-linear transfers of energy and cross helicity with the magnetic field inclination, we have gyrotropized the 3D fields, $K_E(\ell)$ and $K_H(\ell)$, about the B_0 axis. Taking into account the results in 6(a)-(f), we use a log-log scale to highlight the non-linear transfers in the highly oblique and parallel directions, where it is expected that the transfers reach their maxima and minima.

In figure 7(a), the gyrotropized non-linear transfer of energy, $K_E(\ell_{\parallel}, \ell_{\perp})$, confirms the preferential development of the direct energy cascade in the directions transverse to the ambient mean field. On the other hand, the inverse energy cascade takes place at large scales, in the quasi-parallel and the quasi-perpendicular directions. Contrary to the direct cascade, the back transfer of energy is dominant in the directions parallel to the mean magnetic field. Furthermore, parallel and perpendicular back transfers are separated by a region of positive K_E . This gap between the two regions with negative K_E values suggests that each of them corresponds to different inverse cascades. An alternative interpretation is that the limited size of the numerical domain suppresses part of the non-linear interactions in the oblique directions at large scales, thus giving the appearance of two independent inverse cascades.

The gyrotropized non-linear transfer of cross helicity in figure 7(b), $K_H(\ell_{\parallel}, \ell_{\perp})$, is qualitatively similar to $K_E(\ell_{\parallel}, \ell_{\perp})$. In both cases, the positive non-linear transfers reach their maximum values in the directions perpendicular to the mean field and two seemingly-independent negative non-linear transfers are present at large scales. The main difference between the energy and cross helicity cascades is whether the positive transfers reach larger values than the negative ones. The latter is the case for the energy, while for cross helicity the opposite occurs. Moreover, unlike for the energy inverse cascades, the negative non-linear transfer of cross helicity in the perpendicular directions reach similar values than in the quasi-parallel directions.

The complementarity of the energy and cross helicity transfers can be explained as a consequence of the coupling between the two cascades. As pointed out in (Andrés et al. 2022), the coupling appears naturally in the classical formulation of the KHM equations. Dimensional analysis of equation 7 shows that the divergence of the flux of third order structure functions (the main contributor to the cascade rate) can be written in terms of energy and cross helicity,

$$K_H \approx (u \cdot H - B \cdot E/2)/L \quad (26)$$

where $H = u \cdot B$ and $E \approx (u^2 + B^2)/2 \approx u^2$. The same can be done for the energy non-linear transfer using the term $\nabla \cdot Y$ in equation (4) of (Hellinger et al. 2021) and assuming

incompressibility,

$$K_E \approx (2u \cdot E - 2B \cdot H)/L \quad (27)$$

Equations 26 and 27 suggest that an increase of energy would also increase the non-linear transfer of energy while decreasing that of cross helicity, while the opposite would be true for an increase of cross helicity. However, changes of sign in velocity, magnetic field or cross helicity can alter this relation and induce further differences, such as the negative non-linear transfer of cross helicity having similar values in the parallel and perpendicular directions.

5. DISCUSSION

We have used an alternative method to compute the KHM terms for various quantities, namely energy and cross helicity for CMHD and energy, cross helicity and the pseudo-energies for incompressible MHD. Instead of expressing the non-linear transfer as a flux of third order structure functions (*classic KHM*, hereafter), we computed all KHM terms as second order structure functions using eq. 9 (*alternative KHM*). Both approaches are mathematically consistent and numerically equivalent (not shown), but the alternative approach reduces significantly the numerical cost of computing the KHM terms. It also provides, as by-product of the calculation, the terms of the spectral transfer equations (Grete et al. (2017), Hellinger et al. (2021)), that allow to compute the non-linear transfers in Fourier space.

We have made use of the numerical efficiency of the alternative approach to compute all terms of the KHM equations for energy and cross helicity with data from 3D CMHD simulations with high cross helicity. We remark the following results from our analysis of the KHM terms:

1. The onset for the energy cascade takes a shorter time than cross helicity. The time-shift is approximately a turnover time and is not affected by the presence of a mean magnetic field. A phenomenological model for the cross helicity dissipation rate developed in (Yokoi 2011), allows to relate the longer onset period for the cross-helicity cascade with their heating rates. According to such model, the characteristic non-linear times for energy and cross-helicity can be assumed to be:

$$\tau_E = C_{E0} Q_E^{-1/3} k^{-2/3} \quad (28)$$

$$\tau_H = C_{H0} Q_H^{-1/3} k^{-2/3} \quad (29)$$

where C_{E0} and C_{H0} are numerical factors. The inequality $\tau_H > \tau_E$ is fulfilled if $(C_{E0}/C_{H0}) < (Q_H/Q_E)^{-1/3}$. If the numerical constants are equal, that only leaves as a condition that the heating rate for energy has to be larger than for cross helicity. The latter is fulfilled for

both of our runs, as shown in figures 1(c) and 1(d). The similar time-shift between the onsets for both runs despite having different ratios Q_H/Q_E suggests that the condition $C_{E0} = C_{H0}$ can be weakened.

The existence of a time-shift between the energy and cross helicity cascades implies that turbulence shall not be considered as fully developed in the system until the slowest cascade has reached stationarity, since the properties of the fastest cascade can still be affected by changes in the slower one. This can be of importance for certain phenomena in the heliosphere, particularly in situations where high cross helicity winds interact with low cross helicity plasmas, such as the magnetosphere. Recently, a causal link has been found between the longer duration of the recovery phase of geomagnetic storms and the arrival solar wind streams with large cross helicity after the solar-drivers of the storms (Telloni et al. 2021). The need of more time for the cross helicity cascade to fully develop in the magnetosphere could be related to the longer period needed by the magnetosphere to recover its properties previous to the arrival of the solar-driver. The KHM equation for cross helicity derived in this work for CMHD could be applied on numerical simulations of the magnetosphere to verify this relation.

2. In presence of a mean magnetic field, the non-linear transfer of energy and cross helicity split into a positive transfer at intermediate scales and a negative one at large scales. While energy is positive definite and therefore the sign of the non-linear transfer determines the direction of the cascade, this correspondence cannot be made to unsigned definite quantities such as cross helicity. The negative non-linear transfer of cross helicity that we observe in our simulations could correspond to either an inverse cascade of cross helicity or a direct cascade of negative cross helicity.

Since fluctuations are freely decaying in our simulations, it is difficult to identify the generation of large scale structures in real space that would characterize an inverse cascade. However, the analysis of the KHM terms allows to discriminate between the inverse cascade of cross helicity and a direct cascade of negative cross helicity at large scales.

On the one hand, a direct transfer of negative cross helicity would change the sign of the other KHM terms and of the cross helicity heating Q_H . Since the other KHM terms of cross helicity keep their sign when normalized to Q_E , as shown in figure 3, we can discard that the non-linear transfer of cross helicity cascades in the same direction at all scales.

Figure 6. 1D cuts of the KHM terms in the plane xy for run B at $t = 8t_{NL}^0$. The angle θ_B indicates the inclination of the cut with respect to the mean field, with $\theta_B = 0^\circ$ corresponding to the cut along the mean field axis. Panels (a), (b) and (c) corresponds to the KHM terms for energy and panels (d), (e) and (f) to cross-helicity. The color code is the same one used in 3.

Figure 7. (a) Gyrotropization of $K_E(\ell)/Q_E$ for run B at time $8t_{NL}^0$. (b) Gyrotropization of $K_H(\ell)/Q_H$ for run B at time $8t_{NL}^0$.

On the other hand, the analysis of the KHM terms for the pseudo-energies also supports that the incompressible part of the negative non-linear transfer of cross helicity at large scales corresponds to an inverse cascade. Like energy, the pseudo-energies are also positive definite quantities and thus the sign of their non-linear transfer indicates the direction of their cascades. Hence, we identified that at large scales, the initially dominant pseudo-energy E^+ has an inverse cascade while E^- keeps a small direct cascade. In other words, a larger imbalance between both Alfvénic populations is being created at large scales.

Negative values of the non-linear transfers of the energy and the cross helicity cascade have been measured in certain solar wind intervals, where positive and negative values of the cascade rates alternate, displaying patchy inertial ranges (Smith et al. 2009; Stawarz et al. 2010; Coburn et al. 2015; Smith et al. 2018; Vasquez et al. 2018). It has been argued that one possible mechanism leading to this phenomenon in the solar wind could be the formation of large-scale 2D layers in a plasma flow with a strong background magnetic field (Sorriso-Valvo et al. 2007). Indeed, the coexistence of direct and inverse energy cascades have been observed to take place when flows suffer some degree of two-dimensionalization, such as turbulence in thin layers (Musacchio & Boffetta 2017; Alexakis & Biferale 2018) or in strongly rotating 3D fluids (Morize et al. 2005; Mininni & Pouquet 2009). In run B, the inverse cascades take place at the injection scales, where

the initial fluctuations were not excited in the direction parallel to the mean field. The persistence of such initial 2D large scale structures, favored by the presence of an intense mean magnetic field, could have triggered the inverse cascades. At the same time, the development of a strong parallel back transfer of cross helicity at large scales may have also contributed to weaken the energy cascade in the parallel direction, where the non-linear interactions are less efficient, thus acting in benefit of the two-dimensionalization of the flow. Our results are therefore compatible with the interpretation made in (Sorriso-Valvo et al. 2007) about the origin of the inverse transfer patches in the measurements of the cascade rate. However, further study is needed to determine to what extent the initialization with solenoidal fluctuations, the background magnetic field and cross helicity contribute to the inverse cascades.

3. The comparison between the KHM terms of energy and cross helicity for compressible MHD with their corresponding versions for incompressible MHD has shown that the contribution of the compressible fluctuations to non-linear transfers depends on the direction of the cascade.

On the one hand, for the direct cascades of energy and cross helicity, the contribution of compressible fluctuations is small, but not negligible. In our simulations, with a Mach number close to 0.6 at the moment of measuring the KHM terms, the compressible contribution increases the direct non-linear transfer of energy and cross helicity about a 10% of their respective heating rates. This result agrees qualitatively with solar wind measurements of the energy cascade rate (cf. Hadid et al. (2017)).

On the other hand, compressible contributions reduce the back transfer of energy, while enhance the inverse cascade of cross helicity. These compressible contributions can be identified in the classic KHM formulation of the non-linear transfer of cross helicity as the

ones associated to the Laplace force and the divergence of velocity (second and third term of equation 7). Similar terms have been associated to the production of cross helicity in transport models for CMHD (Yokoi 2013). Yet, how these terms translate into real space in a way that benefits the back transfer of cross helicity is unclear. One would expect that compressible fluctuations would be unaffected by the two-dimensionalization of the flow that leads to the back transfers of energy and cross helicity, thus, showing the same effect on the non-linear transfers across all scales. The analysis of KHM term in CMHD simulations in thin-layer domains could help to better understand the contribution of compressible fluctuations to the direct and inverse cascades.

We conclude that the study of the KHM equations for energy and cross helicity in 3D CMHD simulations has shown that the cascades of both quantities are qualitatively similar in many respects, namely turbulence anisotropy or the splitting of the cascades and the contribution of compressible fluctuations to the cascade rates. On the other hand, quantitative differences are striking and their relation to physical phenomena observed in the solar wind and the magnetosphere have been proposed. Thus, the KHM equations are a useful tool that allows for a deeper understanding of turbulent dynamics. In future works, we will extend their use to study the properties of generalized helicity at inertial and kinetic scales.

- 1 V. M.-C. is supported by a PPLZ post-doctoral fellowship
- 2 from the Czech Academy of Sciences. L.F. is supported by
- 3 the UK Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC)
- 4 grant ST/T00018X/1. The authors acknowledge access to
- 5 CESNET storage facilities provided by the project “e-INFRA
- 6 CZ” under the programme “Projects of Large Research, De-
- 7 velopment, and Innovations Infrastructures” LM2018140).
- 8 The authors thank the reviewer for their useful comments and
- 9 suggestions.

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